

An Update on African Elephant *Loxodonta Africana* in the Chinko/Mbari Drainage Basin, Central African Republic

R. Hickisch^{1,*} and T. Aebischer²

¹Social Ecology Research Group, Vienna

²Institute of Ecology and Evolution, University of Bern

January 22, 2013

Figure 1 – Under pressure Although not in the same time period, African Elephants in the Chinko/Mbari Drainage Basin have been photographed in the same site, where poachers passed through later in the rainy season.

In this contribution to the elephant database we present data that we collected in the Central African Republic (CAR) in 2012. We detected tracks

*Corresponding emails to raffael.hickisch@gmail.com

and dung of African Elephant when walking more than 500 km of standardised line transects, and captured photographs in a camera trapping study, originally tailored to estimate abundance of leopard by *spatially explicit capture/recapture*.¹ As the scientific knowledge on eastern CAR is generally scarce, we will first briefly introduce the area, before presenting the elephant records resulting from our expeditions in 2012. The Chinko drainage, together with the headwaters of the rivers Kotto, Mbari and Ouarra contain a virtually uninhabited area of about 70'000 sq km. The wood savannah and tropical lowland rainforest in this ecotone are among the most pristine and continuous ecosystems in Africa. These ecosystems maintain viable, diverse populations of large and medium sized mammals, as well as a plethora of other organisms (Aebischer and Hickisch, in press; Roulet et al., 2007). Most large and medium sized mammals still occur in considerable numbers. We recorded more than 62 different species of large and medium sized mammals, thereof 21 cloven-hoofed species and 10 primates. Carnivore records include an unknown population of the endangered African Wild Dog *Lycaon pictus* (Hickisch and Aebischer, in press) - a population of particular importance for global conservation actions (Sillero-Zubiri, 2004).

Elephant Records in 2012

We did not find evidence of neither rhinoceros nor giraffe, but documented fresh tracks of elephants distributed throughout the study area (see figure 2). Available data seems, however, insufficient to estimate the local elephant population. We tried to identify individuals on the camera traps, and concluded that we got 10-12 individuals (4 adults, 6-8 sub-adults) in the 22 camera trapping events (we used 1h buckets). Characteristics visible on the camera trapping photographs indicate that we recorded the forest morph of African Elephant (see figure 3).

Human Pressure

The African Elephant population in Central Africa has seen a dramatic decline over the last decades. For the Chinko/Mbari Drainage Basin, Erik Mararv, the owner of *Central African Wildlife Adventures* (CAWA) estimates the elephant population(s) at a few hundreds. In response to the apparently high pressure from heavily armed Sudanese poachers Mararv reports tendencies of elephant moving to the thick forests in the south. More

¹see <http://bit.ly/chinko2012>

Figure 2 – Research Expedition 2012 We conducted more than 500 km of line transect by foot, applying *distance sampling* and *track based indices*) and had more than 50 Bushnell camera traps installed, covering an area of roughly 240 sq km. All track and dung records are from spring 2012 - in December we observed fresh tracks further south east, but failed to document precisely. An interactive map is available online at http://bit.ly/chinko2012_elephant_map

Figure 3 – *Loxodonta Africana (forest morph)* On the more than 700 camera trap photographs, several characteristics are typical for forest elephant, i.e. the short, straight and very yellow tusk, or the tight, relatively small ears.

open areas are obviously not visited before the beginning of the rainy season. The fact that we have camera trap photos of African Elephant only during the rainy season, and only in (or at edge of) rainforest confirms this assumption. Elephant poachers (apparently from Sudan) have been recorded in several events (see figure 1) - another sign of high human pressure on *Loxodonta Africana*.

Further Research and Conservation Possibilities

Camera trapping for population estimates appears a reasonable and efficient option in the Central African savannah/rainforest ecotone. In early 2013 we have started another camera trapping study, a project which shall not only deliver interesting insights and abundance data on the Bongo ante-

lope *Tragelaphus eurycerus*, but also test and validate the camera trapping methodology.² As soon as available we will report any further information on *Loxodonta Africana* in the Chinko/Mbari Drainage Basin.

Together with CAWA we thus propose the *Chinko Project*, a long term conservation effort for the 17,600 sq km of the still functioning ecosystem in the Chinko/Mbari drainage basin.³ Situated centrally between the *elephant refuges* in the national parks west (*Zakouma* in Chad and *Bamingui-Bangoran St. Floris* in northwest of CAR) and east (*Garamba* in Dem. Rep. Kongo, *Southern National Park* in South Sudan) the Chinko Project core area may provide an important linking refuge for migrating *Loxodonta Africana* - particularly so, as the effectiveness of *Southern National Park* is very uncertain.

References Cited

Aebischer, T. and R. Hickisch, in press: An update on large and medium sized mammals in the Chinko/Mbari drainage basin, Central African Republic.

Hickisch, R. and T. Aebischer, in press: Proof of an unknown population of *Lycaon pictus* in the Central African Republic. *Canid SSC Newsletter*.

IUCN, 2012: IUCN protected planet. <http://www.protectedplanet.net/>.

Roulet, P. A., C. Pelissier, G. Patek, D. Beina, and J. Ndallot, 2007: Projet zemongo - un aperçu du contexte écologique et de la pression anthropique sur les ressources naturelles de la réserve de faune de zemongo.

Sillero-Zubiri, C., 2004: *Canids, foxes, wolves, jackals, and dogs*. World Conservation Union.

²see http://bit.ly/chinko2012_bongo

³More details for this project are available at http://bit.ly/chinko_management and later this year also on <http://chinkoproject.com>.